

USING DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO ESP LEARNERS

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Abstract.

This article discusses the specifics of effective vocabulary instruction for language for special purpose (ESP) learners. We know that vocabulary plays an important role in learning any language. Learners are constantly acquiring new words, either consciously or unconsciously. Vocabulary teaching in ESP should not be different from teaching vocabulary in EGP. ESP teachers should start by teaching words that belong to common language but are also used regularly in technical language. Vocabulary knowledge in history is limited to memorized lists of specialized words and reading and translating specialized texts. Many modern learning strategies and methods have been developed by scientists and experienced teachers to help improve language skills. Specific goals can be achieved if ESP teachers choose appropriate vocabulary teaching methods based on the specific needs of their students.

Keywords.

language skills, specific vocabulary, technical terms, language learning for ESP, teaching methods, teaching strategies.

Introduction. English has developed into the international language and is spread all over the world into nearly all the fields like science, engineering and technology, business, commerce, scientific exploration, internet, film industry tourism and education and other fields of our life. People learn languages when they have chance to understand and work with language in a context that they comprehend and find intriguing. In this view, ESP is an important means for such opportunities. Learners will acquire English as they can use in their professional work or further studies. In Uzbekistan, in all higher education institutions, English is widely studied for two different purposes: general and specific purposes, and we know that there are specific differences and aspects of learning for these two purposes. In ESP, English should be presented not as a subject to be learned in isolation from real use, nor as a mechanical skill or habit to be developed. On the other hand, English should be presented in authentic contexts to make the learners

acquainted with the particular ways in which the language is used in functions that they will need to perform in their field of specialty or jobs. ESP learners are generally extremely motivated adults with knowledge and experience in their particular fields or students being trained for a future career. Their requirements and thus the methods of tutoring might be veritably distinctive from those of ordinary learners of English as a second language. Consequently we can state that ESP focuses more on vocabulary in context than on teaching alphabet, grammar and language structures, as the students are learning the language integrated into their relative field of study that is important to them “ in order to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform particular job- related functions ”(Fiorito, 2006)[1]. ESP instructors may face several difficulties and challenges while teaching vocabulary, so that in this article I'll try to find some effective ways to educate specific vocabulary to students.

Literary review. Achieving proficiency in the English language is vital for professional success internationally. While a General English course offers learners the opportunity to become fluent in the language, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) provides content altered according to the needs of the learner and the requirements of their profession. Furthermore, the learner is expected to have basic English language proficiency prior to starting the course as ESP focuses on task-specific vocabulary and communication.

Coffey (1985) [2]. described ESP as a “quick and economical” method of using the English language for efficient communication in employment or for the intention of academic learning. ESP focuses on the development of English language communication skills customized according to the required sector or department of the learner, i.e. Finance, Hospitality, Marketing, Computing, Business, Tourism, Medicine etc. It focuses on a particular field, allowing learners to master the skills relevant to their professional needs and, therefore, improve communication.

Teaching vocabulary in ESP learners differs from teaching general English vocabulary. It has some specific features that teachers should take into consideration. Most of the students taking ESP identify it with specific terminology related to their field of study. There are degrees of technicality depending on how restricted a word is to a particular area (Nation, 2001, p. 198) [3]. ESP is seen as an approach rather than a product, by which is meant that ESP does not involve a particular kind of language, teaching material or methodology. So, ESP relates to the learners, the language needed and the literacy environment, and therefore establishes the primacy of need. Need is defined by the reasons for which the

student is learning English (Dudley-Evans and St John, 1998). [4] Nation claims that “technical vocabulary” is a type of specialized vocabulary and its occurrence is affected by factors that influence the use of all vocabulary. Language teachers should prepare their learners to deal with the large numbers of technical words that occur in specialized texts (Nation, 2001). McCarthy (1990, p. viii) [5] points out that “No matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of L2 are mastered, without words to express a wider range of meanings, communication in an L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way” (McCarthy 1990, p. viii). It's my opinion that language preceptors who educate ESP courses should be familiar with the core vocabulary of the field of study and design classes that integrate both content area and English language. Dudley-Evans and St John (1998) are of the opinion that teaching ESP vocabulary is the same as teaching English for General Purposes. The only distinction that should be made is between the vocabulary for comprehension and the vocabulary for production. There are other distinctions: grammatical vs lexical words, cognates vs non-cognates, etc. They further suggest using cognates to deal with technical vocabulary. Kavaliauskienė and Janulevičienė (2000) [6] suggest that the lexical approach is very useful in teaching ESP. Most learners equate ‘vocabulary’ with ‘words’, and there is a tendency among learners to translate any professional text word-for-word, i.e. they usually try to simplify most lexical phrases to separate words. The role of teachers is to raise students’ awareness of the existence of larger lexical items. It is believed that ESP combines subject matter and English language teaching. This approach can be highly motivating for learners because students are able to apply what they learn in their English classes to their main field of study, whether it be education, computing, business, tourism, banking, etc. Being suitable to use the vocabulary and structures that they learn in a meaningful context reinforces what is taught and develop their motivation. Though, ESP concentrates more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures. Another intriguing fact is that ESP words are perceived as more complex than general words, and they should spend more time learning them. This is probably due to the fact that collocations are veritably frequent in ESP and combining them appropriately requires further work. There are concrete types of terms in ESP which bring students’ mistakes due to a lack of translational equivalence between the students’ first language and the second language. Teachers must help the learner become familiar with ESP collocations, and such familiarity will develop best when the learner is consciously aware of this tendency of words to go together (Lewis, 1993). Morgan and Rinvold (2004) [7] believe that the new words are not

learned mechanically, but associatively. Sysoyev (2000) [8] points out that “Vygotsky mentioned the notion of a mediator - a person who hands students achieve what they cannot fulfil by themselves. In teaching ESP, the role of mediator will be placed on the teacher, who will start from students’ current stage and bring them to the next stage of their needs”. The challenge for teachers is to systematize the vocabulary in English. Developments in technology will help us in collecting and analyzing current and specialized corpora (ESP), and both spoken and academic English in order to develop better descriptions of lexical phrases and collocations (Sökmen, 1997) [9]. Language learning techniques and strategies can support all aspects of language learning that is why the teachers should encourage students to use different methods to learn ESP and general English words. Many strategies are non-observable but learners and teachers can debate them or design questionnaires to find more information and make more use of it. Experimenters and scholars should put more effort into designing tools that could provide more information on the usage of non-observable strategies. Nation (1997) was among the first researchers who developed vocabulary learning strategies, and he points out that vocabulary learning strategies should involve choice, i.e., there are several strategies to choose from; be complex, i.e., there are several steps to learn; require knowledge and benefit from training; increase the efficiency of vocabulary learning and vocabulary use. Therefore, some possible vocabulary learning strategies that can be used in teaching ESP vocabulary are the following: synonyms/ antonyms, learning words by categories, by topic, by word families and also vocabulary cards. The results of the studies have shown the existing difficulties in teaching and learning vocabulary such as the lack of background knowledge and cultural understanding, poor ability to understand technical terms, and unsuitable teaching material. Dealing with all types of ESP vocabulary is too broad a topic for a study this size. Specialized vocabulary, not grammar, should be put to the centre of the ESP classroom in order to help learners achieve their goal: to communicate fluently in a job-related real situation in a multinational surrounding.

English for specific purposes (ESP) is a subset of English as a second or foreign language. It usually refers to teaching the English language to university students or people already in employment, with reference to the particular vocabulary and skills they need. The first role of an ESP teacher is following an adulthood-oriented approach toward ESP programs concerned with acting as a simultaneous teacher and counselor. The second prominent role of an ESP teacher is cooperating and collaborating with content teachers to design and teach the materials effectively.

Materials play a crucial role in ESP and have received considerable attention in the literature of the subject. They depend on the methodologies adopted, forming with them “the interface between teaching and learning, or the points at which the course needs, objectives and syllabuses are made tangible to both learners and teachers” (Hyland, 2006: 89) [10]. Selecting ESP materials persuades the running of the course and underlines content of the lesson. Good material should benefit teacher in organizing the course or what is more it can function as an introduction into the new learning techniques, and help teachers and learners in the process of learning. Materials are also a kind of teacher reflection, “they should truly reflect what you think and feel about the learning process. Good material should be based on different interesting texts and activities providing a wide range of skills. Teachers determines which aspects of ESP learning will be aimed on but one piece of material can serve for developing more than one skill, e.g. reading, listening, vocabulary etc. Materials should also function as a link between already learnt and new information. Teaching and learning materials can be;

- text books
- postcards
- films
- radio programs
- multimedia
- digital learning resources including video, audio, text, animations and images.

Some materials contain a general English that is no appropriate with ESP syllabus because students need text about computer systems because they want to improve their

vocabularies, information and knowledge about computer systems. The student can improve their knowledge about computer systems by learning this book. Students not only learn about skill that they use in job but also got information about computer systems in this book. Therefore, this book is efficient to improve students’ skill and knowledge about computer systems. It is important for their job as a software developer. Based on the syllabus, the teachers should design materials that can be used by the ESP students. The materials should design to improve not only vocabulary but listening, reading and speaking skills too. We know reading skills involve skimming, scanning, and guessing word meaning from context. Building vocabulary takes in exercises of matching, filling in the blank and answer question of the text. Based on the need analysis, the teachers can get texts from internet, textbook by adapting and adopting.

Implementing vocabulary techniques and activities in the ESP classroom

If vocabulary building is determined as the central purpose of the ESP class, there are countless techniques that help in this regard. Teachers can mix methodologies or select only those aspects they feel can help their learners. It is important to teach vocabulary in such a way as to help learners make sense of future problems and encourage continuous learning. The effective vocabulary activity should lead learners to pay attention to language features, and help them process those features in profound and thoughtful ways. Finally, these vocabulary-focused activities should take into account the development of all the four skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing. In the last strand, the learners' aim is to receive and convey messages.

Teaching a diverse range of English vocabulary is indeed an essential part of any student's growth. But it doesn't have to be done in isolation. Enhance all vocabulary lessons by building the four major language skills – speaking, listening, reading and writing—at the same time. The following are some vocabulary learning and teaching techniques that can be applied:

Memorizing Memory strategies involve relating the word to be retained with some previously learned knowledge – that is facilitating the storage and retrieval of words.

Visualization is one particularly powerful memorization strategy. As Nattinger (1988)

[11] observes, “words in our mental lexicon are tied to each other not only by meaning form and sound but also by sight.”

Repetition and Recycling Words Due to the fact that there are many aspects to learn about a word, a single encounter with it makes it highly improbable it will be learned or retained.

Brainstorming Activities Doing brainstorming activities is another way to help

increase a learner's vocabulary. This process generally refers to brainstorming associations that a word has with other words and then diagramming the results. For example, when asked to give words learners thought of when they hear the word 'computer', most learners would generate a number of words and phrases: device, input, output, peripheral devices etc.

- **Crossword** It is one of the most widely known programs and it works similarly to text-based puzzles. It depends on the ability of the teacher in creating puzzles with the target vocabulary for his/her classes.

- **Wordspin** Used for word recognition and often considered as a 'speller trainer'. In this program the learners have to identify a word 'spinning' on the screen.

- **Alphagame** An alphabetical order game in which the learner has to 'guess' the word the computer is thinking of by typing words and finding out whether it is after or before in the dictionary based on the computer target.

- **Word definition** Introduction of technical terms. The teacher or one of students give the definition for any technical word, the others try to guess this word.

- **Scrabble** It is a very effective computer game which usually includes around 20.000 build-in words in its dictionary with the possibility of introducing others for working as an authoring tool.

- **Synonyms and antonyms** Using synonyms and antonyms is another way of grouping words. It can also be very useful to record synonyms together so that when you are writing or speaking you are able to use a variety of language and not just the same word again and again.

The given activities can be used for any directions of ESP teaching and of course help our learners not to improve only vocabulary but as well as other major language skills too.

Conclusions. The ESP course must be based on and extend the foundations for proper communication. It must extend the learner's grammatical, lexical and functional skills and cover the public, educational and professional skills.

In order to teach English for special purposes, the teacher needs to have not only knowledge of the English language, but also knowledge of the professional sphere of his students, in order to successfully master their communication skills in their professional activities in English.

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